

REDUCTION FORMULAE FOR $\int \sin^m x \cos^n x dx$

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Annotation. Using this formula $\int \sin^m x \cos^n x dx$, we can simplify the processes [1-2] specified by physical, biological, and mathematical formulas. In addition, the given integral formula allows you to optimize the calculation process.

Keywords. simplify the formula.

In some processes or practical problems we encounter integral equations [1]. Simplification of these processes is important for us. We will consider some of them through the following examples [1]. Suppose that this integral has a domain of definition.

$$\begin{aligned} \int \sin^m x \cos^n x dx &= \int \sin^{m-1} x \cos^n x \sin x dx = \sin^{m-1} x \cdot \left(\frac{-\cos^{n+1} x}{n+1} \right) - \int (m-1) \sin^{m-2} x \cos x \left(\frac{\cos^{n+1} x}{n+1} \right) dx = \\ &= -\frac{\sin^{m-1} x \cos^{n+1} x}{n+1} + \frac{m-1}{m+1} \int \sin^{m-2} x \cos^n x (1 - \sin^2 x) dx = \\ &= -\frac{\sin^{m-1} x \cos^{n+1} x}{n+1} + \frac{m-1}{m+1} \int \sin^{m-2} x \cos^n x dx - \frac{m-1}{m+1} \int \sin^m x \cos^n x dx \end{aligned}$$

Transposing the last term to the left and dividing by $1 + \frac{m-1}{n+1}$, i.e., $\frac{m+n}{n+1}$, we obtain the reduction formula

$$\int \sin^m x \cos^n x dx = -\frac{\sin^{m-1} x \cos^{n+1} x}{m+n} + \frac{m-1}{m+n} \int \sin^{m-2} x \cos^n x dx \tag{1}$$

(a) when m is odd, put $\cos x = t$, when n is odd, put $\sin x = t$

(b) when m and n both are even integers, express the integrand as a series of cosines of multiple angles and integrate term by term if m and n are small, otherwise use the method of reduction formulae.

To show that

$$I_{m,n} = \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \sin^m x \cos^n x dx = \frac{(m-1)(m-3)\dots(n-1)(n-3)\dots}{(m+n)(m+n-2)(m+n-4)\dots} \times \left(\frac{\pi}{2}, \text{only if both } m \text{ and } n \text{ are even} \right)$$

From (1) we have

$$I_{m,n} = \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \sin^m x \cos^n x dx = -\frac{\sin^{m-1} x \cos^{n+1} x}{m+n} \Bigg|_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} + \frac{m-1}{m+n} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \sin^{m-2} x \cos^n x dx$$

$$I_{m,n} = \frac{m-1}{m+n} I_{m-2,n}$$

Case I. when m is odd

Similarly, $I_{m-2,n} = \frac{m-3}{m+n-2} I_{m-4,n}; \quad I_{m-4,n} = \frac{m-5}{m+n-4} I_{m-6,n};$

$$I_{5,n} = \frac{4}{n+5} I_{3,n}$$

Finally

(2)

$$I_{3,n} = \frac{2}{n+3} I_{1,n} = \frac{2}{n+3} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \sin x \cos^n x dx = \frac{2}{n+3} \left| -\frac{\cos^{n+1} x}{n+1} \right|_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} = \frac{2}{(n+3)(n+1)}$$

From these , we obtain $I_{m,n} = \frac{(m-1)(m-3)(m-5) \dots \cdot 4 \cdot 2}{(m+n)(m+n-2)(m+n-4) \dots \cdot (n+3)(n+1)}$

Case II. When m is even, we have

$$I_{m-2,n} = \frac{m-3}{m+n-2} I_{m-4,n}; \quad I_{m-4,n} = \frac{m-5}{m+n-4} I_{m-6,n}$$

$$I_{4,n} = \frac{3}{n+4} I_{2,n}; \quad I_{2,n} = \frac{1}{n+2} I_{0,n} = \frac{1}{n+2} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \cos^n x dx$$

From these, we have

$$I_{m,n} = \frac{(m-1)(m-1)(m-1) \dots 1}{(m+n)(m+n-2)(m+n-4) \dots (n+2)} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \cos^n x dx = \frac{(m-1)(m-1)(m-1) \dots 1}{(m+n)(m+n-2)(m+n-4) \dots (n+2)} \cdot \frac{(n-1)(n-3) \dots}{n(n-2) \dots} \times \left(\frac{\pi}{2} \text{ only if } n \text{ is even} \right)$$

Combining (2) and (3), we get the desired result.

References

1. Lester R. Ford, Calculus mcgraw-Hill via hathitrust 1963.
2. Mellen W. Haskell, on the introduction of the notion of hyperbolic functions, Bulletin of the American Mathematical Society 1895.